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Abstract. Currently, knowing two or more languages is common because of different reasons. This article is just about bilingualism.

Key words: language, bilingualism, mastery, comprehension, community, ability, fluent

Annotatsiya. Hozirgi vaqtda ikki yoki undan ortiq tilni bilish turli sabablarga ko'ra keng tarqalgan. Ushbu maqola shunchaki bilingvizm haqida.

Kalit so'zlar: til, ikki tillilik, mahorat, tushunish, jamiyat, qobiliyat, ravon

Аннотация. В настоящее время знание двух или более языков является распространенным явлением по разным причинам. Эта статья как раз о двуязычии.

Ключевые слова: язык, двуязычие, мастерство, понимание, сообщество, способность, свободное владение

Bilingualism is not a phenomenon of language; it is a characteristic of its use. It is not a feature of the code but of the message. It does not belong to the domain of “langue” but of “parole”. If language is the property of the group, bilingualism is the property of the individual. An individual's use of two languages supposes the existence of two different language communities; it does not suppose the existence of a bilingual community. The bilingual community can only be regarded as a dependent collection of individuals who have reasons for being bilingual. A self-sufficient bilingual community has no reason to remain bilingual, since a closed community in which everyone is fluent in two languages could get along just as well with one language. As long as there are different monolingual communities, however, there is likelihood of contact between them; this contact results in bilingualism.

The concept of bilingualism has become broader and broader since the beginning of the twentieth century. It was long regarded as the equal mastery of two languages; and this is the definition still found in certain glossaries of linguistics, e.g., “Qualité d'un sujet ou d'une population qui se sert couramment de deux langues, sans aptitude marquée pour l'une plutôt que pour l'autre” (Marouzeau, 1951). Bloomfield considered bilingualism as “the native-like control of two languages” (Bloomfield, 1933:56). This was broadened by Haugen to the ability to produce “complete meaningful utterances in the other language” (Haugen, 1953: vol. 1, p. 7). And it has now been suggested that the concept be further extended to include simply “passive-knowledge” of the written language or any “contact with possible models in a second language and the ability to use these in the environment of the native language” (Diebold, 1961:111). This broadening of the concept of bilingualism is due to realization that the point at which a speaker of a second language becomes bilingual is either arbitrary or impossible to determine. It seems obvious, therefore, that if we are to study the phenomenon of bilingualism we are forced to consider it as something entirely relative (Mackey, 1956:8). We must, moreover, include the use not only of two languages, but of any number of languages (Mackey, 1959). We shall therefore consider bilingualism as the alternate use of two or more languages by the same individual. What does this involve? Since bilingualism is a relative concept, it involves the question of DEGREE. How well does the individual know the languages he uses? In other words, how bilingual is he? Second, it involves the question of FUNCTION. What does he use his languages for? What role have his languages played in his total pattern of behaviour? Third, it includes the question of ALTERNATION. To what extent does he alternate between his languages? How does he change from one language to the other, and under what conditions? Fourth, it includes the question of INTERFERENCE. How well does the bilingual keep his languages apart? To what extent does he

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fuse them together? How does one of his languages influence his use of the other? Bilingualism is a behavioural pattern of mutually modifying linguistic practices varying in degree, function, alternation, and interference. It is in terms of these four inherent characteristics that bilingualism may be described.

The first and most obvious thing to do in describing a person's bilingualism is to determine how bilingual he is. He may indeed be able to understand both languages equally well; but he may be unable to speak both of them with equal facility. Since the language skills of the bilingual may include differences in comprehension and expression in both the spoken and written forms, it is necessary to test each of these skills separately if we are to get a picture of the extent of his bilingualism. If, however, we are only interested in determining his bilingualism rather than in describing it, other forms of tests are possible: word-detection tests, word-association and picture-vocabulary tests, for example, have been used for this purpose (Peal and Lambert, 1962:76). The bilingual's mastery of a skill, however, may not be the same at all linguistic levels. He may have a vast vocabulary but a poor pronunciation, or a good pronunciation but imperfect grammar. In each skill, therefore, it is necessary to discover the bilingual's mastery of the phonology (or graphics), the grammar, the vocabulary, the semantics, and the stylistics of each language. What has to be described is proficiency in two sets of related variables, skills, and levels. Bilingualism cannot be described within the science of linguistics; we must go beyond. Linguistics has been interested in bilingualism only in so far as it could be used as an explanation for changes in a language, since language, not the individual, is the proper concern of this science. Psychology has regarded bilingualism as an influence on mental processes. Sociology has treated bilingualism as an element in culture conflict. Pedagogy has been concerned with bilingualism in connection with school organization and media of instruction. For each of these disciplines bilingualism is incidental; it is treated as a special case or as an exception to the norm. Each discipline, pursuing its own particular interests in its own special way, will add from time to time to the growing literature on bilingualism (see bibliographies in Weinreich, 1953; Haugen, 1956; Jones, 1960). However, it seems to add little to our understanding of bilingualism as such, with its complex psychological, linguistic, and social interrelationships.

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